

OWNERSHIP STRUCTURE AND CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY DISCLOSURES OF LISTED COMPANIES IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study investigates the relationship between ownership structure and Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosures (CSR) with focus on the impact of managerial ownership, institutional ownership, foreign ownership, and ownership concentration on CSR. One hundred and eighteen (118) companies listed on the Nigeria Stock Exchange (NSE) as of 31st December 2018 was studied from year 2009 to 2018. The data collected was analysed using descriptive statistics, correlation analysis and panel regression analysis. The results indicate that CSR in Nigeria is low with an average CSR of 35% for the studied firms. The correlation results revealed that CSR and foreign ownership have positive correlation, while CSR and the proxies to the independent variables; institutional ownership, managerial ownership and ownership concentration have negative correlation while institutional ownership and ownership concentration have the highest correlation. The regression results suggested that among firms listed on the NSE, managerial ownership and foreign ownership have a significant negative effect on CSR, while institutional ownership and ownership concentration have a significant positive effect on CSR. The study therefore recommends that the voluntary nature of CSR in Nigeria should be enhanced through compulsory disclosure requirements. The Securities and Exchange Commission should ensure companies management do not own large amounts of equity shares, institutional shareholders should own large amounts of equity. Foreign ownership of equity shares should be reduced. Ownership concentration should be encouraged in Nigeria. Institutional shareholders should be allowed and encouraged to have representatives on the board of directors.

Keywords: Ownership Structure, Managerial Ownership, Institutional Ownership, Foreign Ownership and Ownership Concentration.

JEL: M49, M14

1.0 Introduction

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) entails that corporate organisations takes cognisance of social and environmental issues like proper waste disposal and labour welfare in their business activities. Inclusion of social responsibility in the activities of corporations has also brought about the need for corporate organisations to provide information, in their annual financial reports, on how their corporate actions affect society and what steps they are taking to positively affect the society and environment. It is also in the interest of corporate stakeholders that corporations give back to the society in which they have flourished (Yahaya & Apochi, 2021).

Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosures (CSR) in Nigeria is currently a voluntary activity (Adeyemi&Ayanlola, 2015). Its voluntary nature provides corporate organisations the liberty to decide what information to disclose or withhold. This decision on what should be disclosed and how much information should be disclosed has been a challenge for corporations. In corporate organisations, there is usually the interplay of influences on the policies, strategies and decisions of the company. The major influencers are the shareholders and management through the board of directors. Generally, the board of directors is charged with the responsibility of monitoring and controlling the activities of the corporation (Dias, Rodrigues & Craig, 2017). The directors are also charged with preparing the annual financial reports of the company together with disclosing non-financial information. Thus, the board ensures that the corporation is accountable and transparent to its stakeholders.

However, in the board's discharge of its functions, agency problems of conflict between management and shareholders arise, in which management may put their interests above those of the shareholders. Various measures are deemed to mitigate this agency problem. Managerial ownership as a measure is believed to align the interests of management with shareholders. Managerial ownership in a corporation being executives or directors owning stock or shares in the corporation (Chang & Zhang, 2015). This agency problem is believed to be reduced when managers are also owners in the company. The owner managers are believed to place the interests of shareholders as high priority. A second dominant influence that can reduce this agency problem is institutional ownership. Institutional owners include banks, mutual funds, pension funds and insurance companies (Chang & Zhang, 2015). They usually influence the policies, strategies and decisions of corporations through their substantial voting power which is gained through their high number of share investment. With this voting power, institutional owners can choose which directors they want and remove others not working in their interest.

A large number of foreign shareholders can influence the strategies, policies and decisions of a corporation. This ability to influence the actions of a firm's management is basically due to the high expertise and corporate governance skills which foreign shareholders possess (Alrabha,Haija, Alqudah&Azzam, 2018) and also due to the need for foreign owners to protect their investments from risks and uncertainties such as social sanctions which they face in these foreign environments (Khan, Muttakin& Siddiqui, 2013).

High number of share investment by certain groups of investors can however lead to ownership being concentrated in a few hands in corporations. Ownership concentration being a major source of influence among shareholders provides for more effective supervision over a company's management. This more effective supervision over a corporations' management activity is due to the need of large share owners to protect their investment in the company in the long term (Ba, 2017). The major contention is, therefore, how these ownership structure attributes (managerial ownership, institutional ownership, foreign ownership and ownership concentration) interact to affect a company's policies, strategy and decisions on CSR.

While studies have been carried out on CSRD in environmentally sensitive industries like the petroleum (Mohammed, 2018) and manufacturing industries (Egbunike&Tarilaye, 2017) and studies such as Ohidoa, Omokhudu and Oserogho (2016) have also investigated the determinants of CSR information disclosure in Nigeria, there have been few studies such as Yusuf, Fodio and Nwala (2018) and Sadiq and Mohammed (2017) dedicated to the influence of firm ownership structure attributes on CSRD in Nigeria. There have also been mixed results from studies available on the relationship between corporate ownership structure attributes and CSRD such as Kurawa and Kabara (2014) (managerial ownership) finding a negative relationship while Yusuf *et al.* (2018) found a positive relationship.

Ownership structure is nevertheless important as it reflects how power and influence are distributed among the shareholders of a corporation. Against the backdrop that shareholders can influence management decisions and actions through their voting power, this study investigates empirically the relationship between ownership structure and CSRD in Nigeria. This study also contributes to existing literature by using the UNGC as framework for CSRD. This is because very few studies such as Ortas, Alvarez and Garayar (2015) have used it as a measure for CSRD. Rather, studies carried out on CSRD in Nigeria have used various frameworks like the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) (Egbunike&Tarilaye, 2017), GRI4 (Haladu&Salim, 2017) or researchers develop their own CSRD checklists from previous studies carried out (Ahmed, Zakaree&Kolawole, 2016).

2.0 Literature Review

2.1 Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosures

Ahmed *et al.* (2016) defined CSRD as a medium by which corporate organisations provide their stakeholders with information on the effect of their corporate actions on society. Esa and Ghazali (2012) viewed CSRD to be the process of providing information on a company's products, welfare of employees, philanthropy, community involvement and concern for the environment. Thus, CSRD entails corporations providing information to their stakeholders and the public on how CSR is incorporated in the business corporate activities. CSRD is therefore of interest to policy makers and the general community (Yahaya & Apochi, 2021).

The basic idea behind CSRD is explained by Ali and Isa (2018) to be that each stakeholder sees corporations as being responsible for their actions towards them and each of these stakeholders evaluates the extent to which corporations meet this responsibility. In view of this, the writers stated that owners evaluate corporations based on their performance financially, the community assess based on how companies engage in social responsibility, the government uses how corporations comply with the relevant legislations enacted, employees assess based on the company's working conditions and customers use product quality. Hence, Jamali, Safieddine and Rabbath (2008) conclude that companies are therefore charged with including information dealing with CSR in their annual financial reports to satisfy the information needs of their corporation's stakeholders. CSRD focuses on helping corporations meet the ever increasing information needs of stakeholders (Jorah, 2020). Hartikayanti, Trisyandi and Saptono (2016) thus

posits that environmental disclosures are part of CSR activities and are intended as a means which the community and investors can use in economic and political decision making. CSRD has also been seen by Ahmed *et al.* (2016) as a veritable tool used in increasing a company's transparency, accountability and credibility in society. The transparency, accountability and credibility are to be derived from disclosures on environmental and ecological issues, employee welfare, community involvement, energy, consumer and product related issues. Okudo & Amahalu (2021) state that CSRD is a pre-requisite for corporations. CSRD can therefore be concluded to be the provision of information on a corporation's social responsibility actions, for its stakeholders' knowledge and awareness, so as to ensure they have a positive perception of the organisation.

Generally, CSRD can be made voluntarily or mandatorily (Ahmed *et al.*, 2016). Countries such as the Netherlands and France practise mandatory CSRD while countries like Nigeria and Germany practise voluntary CSRD (Adeyemi&Ayanlola, 2015). Mandatory disclosures comprise information on a company's CSR activities that are required by law or regulation while Voluntary disclosures are seen as CSR information which are disclosed but not regulated or required by law. Hence, this study focuses on voluntary disclosures, as CSRD in Nigeria is regarded as voluntary (Adeyemi&Ayanlola, 2015) due to there being no strict regulations on it. Mandatory CSR disclosures while being regulated have been structured by various guidelines in disclosing CSR information. These standard guidelines include; ISO14000 environmental management standard which was developed by International Standard Organisation (ISO) in 1996 and aims at reducing the depletion of natural resources through reduction in their use and to minimize the harmful effect of corporate activities on the soil, water and air. SA8000 standard deals with improving the work environment of corporations and was developed in 1989 by Social Accountability International. Accountability 1000 (AA1000) is aimed at increasing corporation's professional approach towards their establishment, social audits, ethics and standards related to accountability issues and was developed by Account Ability in 1999.

The UNGC (United Nations Global Compact) was given through a United Nations initiative in 2000 and it aims to ensure corporations make decisions and policies in line with sustainability and CSR context. It is divided into ten (10) principles which deal with human rights, labour, environment and anti-corruption. Global Reporting Initiative (GRI), a non-governmental organization founded in 1997, provides guidelines that are suitable for CSRD universally, on corporation's actions relating to their environmental, social and economic activities and the goal of GRI is to develop and promote a universally suitable set of guidelines for CSRD on the environmental, economic and social activities of companies.

2.2 Ownership Structure

Corporate attributes also referred to as firm attributes, corporate characteristics or firm characteristics was defined by Ali and Isa (2018) as the specific features of a company which distinguishes it from another company. This definition infers that every firm has some features or attributes which are particular to it and which differentiates it from other firms. Ali and Isa

(2018) further stated that firm characteristics or the distinguishing features of firms are numerous and can be based on; size, industry type, profitability, nature of business, leverage and geographical location. Mgeni and Nayak (2016) classified corporate attributes into three (3). These classifications they listed to be firstly, structural corporate attributes which include firm size, ownership and age. Secondly, market related corporate attributes which consists of type of industry, environmental uncertainty, and market environment. The third classification being capital related corporate attributes which include firm liquidity and capital intensity.

Managerial ownership, institutional ownership, foreign ownership, and ownership concentration as corporate characteristics adopted for this study, are based on the structural classification. The reason being, they are attributes that influence the ownership structure of companies. This ownership structure can influence a corporation's decision-making structure together with its formulation of policies and strategies. Ownership structure is a corporate governance mechanism which includes corporate policies, guidelines and control systems that are required for the proper management of corporations and for reducing inefficiencies in companies (Jaya, Bambang & Endang, 2017). Ownership structure denotes how the equity shares of a corporation are owned, held and distributed among the various equity shareholders in the corporate organisation. Corporations having a successful relationship with their stakeholders are based on their ownership structure and how the ownership structure affects the firm's operations and execution of its corporate obligations (Li & Zhang, 2010).

According to Uwuigbe, Erin, Igbino and Jafaru (2017), a firm's ownership structure is defined by the total number of equity shares that are owned by the shareholders having the largest number of equity shares divided by the total number of outstanding equity shares. Where the power and authority in a firm resides is generally a reflection of the ownership structure of the firm and this ownership structure also connotes how power is distributed among the shareholders or owners. Jaya *et al.* (2017) believed that a corporation's ownership structure can be used to reduce agency conflicts in corporations as corporate ownership structure affects the process of monitoring in a firm. This monitoring is by way of powerful and dominant shareholders/corporate share owners using their power to influence management decisions through their voting power and therefore determining which decisions are taken by management including decisions on CSR. This study therefore investigated empirically the relationship between ownership structure and CSR, with focus on four (4) ownership structure, attributes namely, managerial ownership, institutional ownership, foreign ownership, and ownership concentration.

2.2.1 Managerial Ownership and Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosures

According to Ba (2017), in order to reduce the conflict of interests between managers and shareholders, managers may be given equity shares to increase their stake in the company. Chang and Zhang (2015) stated that if on one hand, management own a significant number of shares in a corporation, they are more likely to make decisions on corporate matters that maximize shareholder values. They went further to state that on the other hand, management may also

likely take short term decisions that increase the firms profit and also increase managements' power to take decisions in their own interest.

Furthermore, due to the fact that corporate management usually have better information about a company than any other corporate stakeholder, this better information can be used to achieve their personal goals and gain advantage in the company. Corporate management are usually risk averse and prefer to pursue short term less risky business opportunities than shareholders who prefer long term higher risk ventures if the rewards are sufficiently high. Thus, while performing CSR activities, disclosure of these activities may provide long term benefits to shareholders such as the long term sustainability and going concern of the company, management may still prefer corporate activities that provide short term benefits and hence may not carry out much CSR and CSRD. Nevertheless, managerial ownership can induce management to align their interests with other shareholders and thus pursue these long term shareholder values like long term sustainability of investment, competitiveness and profitability of the firm, which performing CSR activities and CSRD may provide.

2.2.2 Institutional Ownership and Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosures

Institutional investors are influential in corporations because they can either significantly change a firm's management or organise the interests of various shareholder groups (Mohamed & Faouzi, 2014). Institutional ownership relates to investments in shares of corporations by institutional investors like banks and pension funds (Chang & Zhang, 2015). Institutional investors, usually have large amounts of fund from various individuals who bring their money together into a pool. These large amounts of funds which are invested give institutional investors significant power and influence in companies. This power and influence is exercised through their voting power and asymmetric information advantages over other shareholders (Chang & Zhang, 2015). Institutional investors, due to their large investments, are also particularly interested in the safety of their investments and also the sustainability and profitability of the companies they invest in. Hence, Jo and Harjoto (2011) state that, institutional investors are better able to monitor the actions of corporations' management and have greater incentives to carry out this monitoring. Ba (2017) buttresses this by saying that institutional investors own a significantly large number of shares and this makes them to be more actively involved in the company's decision making.

Due to the large amount of shares owned by institutional shareholders, it is difficult for them to move their investments out of companies without affecting share prices generally. This creates an incentive for them to monitor very closely the actions and decisions of the companies they invest in. Institutional investors can therefore promote the disclosure of CSR information in order to enable other stakeholders, which includes the public in general, know that the invested companies are socially responsible and hence protect their investment through ensuring the company is protected from social sanctions and criticisms.

2.2.3 Foreign Ownership and Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosures

Foreign ownership in a company can be defined as the number of shares of the company that are owned by foreign parties, which can be private individuals or institutions (Laksmi & Kamila, 2018). The basic idea of the relationship between foreign ownership and CSR is given by Hu, Zhu and Hu (2016) where they opined that CSR developed due to the globalisation and expansion of the world economy, which led to the growth of multinational companies that had great economic power and were owned by foreigners. These multinational companies were described as having extensive effect on the society and this extensive effect required them to accept responsibility for the environment, local employment, safety and local community development, the neglect of which was said could threaten the sustainability of the company.

CSR is also important to foreign owners of corporations due to risks and uncertainties, like the risk of government sanctions and environmental litigation costs arising from information asymmetry. This information asymmetry can be reduced through the disclosing of corporate information which includes CSR information and the risks and uncertainties are stated by Istianingsih (2015) to be due to geographic barriers and language reasons. Thus, Swandari and Sadikin (2016) posited that foreign ownership can be associated with implementing better CSR and therefore better CSR. Therefore, foreign owned companies are more likely to disclose more non-financial information because of the needs and demands of foreigners (Darus, Yusoff, Mohamed & Nejati, 2016).

Nevertheless, in companies where there is concentration of foreign owners from countries and environments where there are little or no CSR or voluntary CSR, there may be the tendency for such investors to influence the company's management to ignore CSR and CSR.

2.3.4 Ownership Concentration and Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosures

Ownership concentration can be described as the amount of equity shares owned by the largest shareholders or block equity holders (Ba, 2017). According to Dias et al. (2017) where ownership is concentrated, there may be pressure on management to respond to the interests of these large shareholders, much to the disadvantage of smaller shareholders. The corporate information that is disclosed is also highly likely to reflect the large shareholders interests rather than the interests of all shareholders and the presence of large shareholders may also limit corporate disclosures (Fathi, 2013). Where ownership concentration is low and ownership more dispersed, the information disclosed is likely to be more effective, especially when shareholders are concerned with a company's social and environmental activities (Chan, Watson & Woodliff, 2014). Hence, when ownership is concentrated in corporations, larger shareholders can carry out effective supervision of management and also improve management ability.

Firms with high ownership concentration are usually associated with low corporate disclosures including CSR. These low disclosures usually stem from the fact that the shareholders who have control over the firm due to their large concentrated shareholdings are able to effectively monitor the activities of management and thus do not need more corporate disclosures and these large equity owners have greater incentive to monitor management due to the need to protect their huge investments and also have the ability to control the decisions and policies of the firm

including its CSRD policies (Khan, Chand & Patel, 2013). Ba (2017) however stated that concentrated ownership of shares in corporations can support CSRD, as the shareholders believe it has a positive effect on the long term value of the firm and their investments in it.

Thus, in corporations where ownership is diffused CSR and CSRD are expected to be major corporate concerns as the companies need to cater for the information needs of a large number of shareholders. Having a larger number of concentrated amounts of equity shares held by shareholders who value CSRD usually leads to high CSRDs but when high amounts of equity shares are held by shareholders who have no regard for CSRD, disclosure of CSR information is usually low.

2.3 Empirical Review

Okudo and Amahalu (2021) examined the relationship between corporate governance and carbon disclosure practices of quoted manufacturing firms in Nigeria from year 2011 to 2020. Panel Least Squares regression analysis revealed that ownership concentration, board gender diversity and sustainability committed have significant positive relationship with carbon emissions disclosure. Yahaya and Apochi (2021) examined the effect of board of directors on CSRD of listed quoted companies in Nigeria. Using panel data of 329 observations from forty-seven (47) firms over seven (7) years (2013-2019). Results showed that board diligence and independence have an insignificant effect on CSRD, while board gender diversity, firm size and leverage have a significant effect. Jorah (2020) investigated the relationship between firm attributes, CSRD and measures of financial performance of twenty-nine (29) NSE listed financial sector firms for ten (10) years (2009-2018). Using Structural Equation Model (SME) technique, firm performance, firm value and capital structure had significant influence on CSRD. Ownership structure and board attributes had significant influence on firm financial performance but not on CSRD. Oshiole, Elamah and Amahalu (2020) examined the effect of environmental disclosure on the profitability of NSE listed oil and gas firms from 2010 to 2019. Panel least square regression analysis showed that waste management disclosure, employee health disclosure, safety cost disclosure and environmental remediation cost disclosure have significant positive effect on net profit margin.

Yusuf *et al.* (2018) studied a sample of 44 financial institutions listed on the NSE from 2008-2017. Probit regression analysis using STATA (Version 13) revealed that block owners had a positive and significant effect on voluntary disclosures while institutional ownership had a negative and no significant effect on voluntary disclosures and managerial ownership had a positive but insignificant relationship with voluntary disclosures. Laksmi and Kamila (2018) also studied state owned corporations listed on the Indonesian Stock Exchange from year 2013 to 2015. Results from a sample of fifty-one (51) companies derived from a population of twenty-two (22) listed firms, using purposive sampling which was based on three (3) criteria. Results from multiple regression analysis showed that managerial ownership has significant negative relationship with CSRD, state ownership has significant positive relationship with

CSRD, foreign ownership has insignificant negative relationship with CSRD while, board composition, audit committee and earnings management have no relationship on CSRD.

Sadiq and Mohammed (2017) studied the impact of corporate ownership structure on the voluntary disclosure of financial service corporations listed on the NSE from 2006 to 2015. From a sample of 28 companies, the results generated from Pearson correlation analysis showed that managerial ownership has a negative association with CSRD while the control variables; firm age, firm size and board size, have positive association with CSRD. OLS regression, however, showed managerial ownership has an insignificant and positive effect on CSRD while control variables; firm age, firm size and board size, have a significant positive relationship with CSRD. Ahmad, Rashid and Gow (2017) investigated the influence of corporate attributes on the CSRD of 450 sample firms listed on the Bursa Malaysia from 2008 to 2013. Board independence, managerial ownership, institutional ownership, company age, return on assets, company size and market capitalisation were used as corporate attributes. Results derived from OLS regression analysis gave that the influence of board independence on CSRD was industry specific. Other corporate attributes; managerial ownership, institutional ownership, company age, company size, return on asset and market capitalisation had a positive significant relationship to CSRD.

Haladu and Salim (2017) investigated, using OLS regression analysis, the effect of various corporate attributes on social and environmental disclosures for sixty-one (61) firms, from the thirteen (13) sectors of the NSE from 2009 to 2014. Results showed that listing on the NSE, firm size, industry type, ownership concentration and environmental expert are positive and significant for both environmental and social disclosures. Companies monitored by the ministry of environment, board composition, financial leverage and firm age, however, are positive but insignificant for both. Social disclosures are better for effective tax rate, Market to book value, audit firm, companies monitored by the Department of Petroleum Resources (DPR) and National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency (NESREA) while Environmental disclosures are better under profitability and CEO duality.

Hu *et al.* (2016) studied a sample of one thousand eight hundred and seventy-two (1872) companies from the total companies listed on China Stock Exchange Market at the end of the year 2010. Using Probit and Tobit regression analysis on the relationship between ownership structure and CSRD and using the year 2011 white paper published by the Chinese Academy of Social Sciences research centre for CSR, state ownership, institutional ownership, foreign ownership, and corporate ownership were all found to have positive relationship with CSRD. Ghabayen, Mohamad and Ahmad (2016) studied the impact of firm board attributes on CSRD in the Jordan banking sector using a sample of 147 publicly listed banks for a period of ten (10) years (2004-2013). The study used a check list of one hundred (100) items on CSRD. Results showed that board size and institutional ownership has a significant negative association with CSRD, independent directors have a negative association with CSRD, female directors have negative association with CSRD, profitability has insignificant association with CSRD, while leverage and liquidity are significant and positively associated.

Chang and Zhang (2015) found that ownership concentration and institutional investors have a significant positive impact on CSRD while managerial ownership has an insignificant negative influence on CSRD. The results were derived from OLS regression analysis of a sample of one hundred and thirty-nine (139) firms in Chinese industries with heavy pollution from 2008 to 2012. Isa and Mohammed (2015) investigated a sample of six (6) companies from food product firms listed on the NSE from 2005-2014 using STATA (version 12) regression analysis. Variables used indicate board independence was significant and positively associated with CSRD, managerial ownership was significant and negatively associated with CSRD, while board size and women on board showed significant positive association with CSRD.

Mohamed and Faouzi (2014) by means of Generalised Least Square (GLS) analysed, a sample of twenty-three (23) non-financial listed companies in Stock Exchange Securities Value of Tunisia, from 2003 to 2011. The results derived showed that CEO duality, board independence and ownership concentration have negative significant relationship with CSRD. Leverage has significant positive relationship with CSRD while profitability has insignificant positive relationship with CSRD, board size and institutional ownership having positive but insignificant relationship with CSRD. Kurawa and Kabara (2014) also examined voluntary disclosures made by companies in the Nigerian petroleum industry downstream sector, from 2001-2010 using STATA (Version 12) regression analysis package. Ownership concentration was found to have significant positive association with voluntary disclosures. Board composition had positive but insignificant association with voluntary disclosures, CEO duality and managerial ownership however, indicated significant negative relationship with voluntary disclosures. The association between ownership concentration in firms, number of shareholders, foreign ownership and board size with CSRD was also studied by Sufian and Zahan (2013). Analysis, with OLS regression, of a sample of one hundred and thirty (130) firms listed on the Dhaka Stock Exchange showed that, ownership concentration had positive association with CSRD. Board size had negative association with CSRD, other variables; foreign ownership and number of shareholders also had no association with CSRD.

Uyar, Kilic and Bayyurt (2013) studied a sample of one hundred and thirty-one (131) corporations listed on the Borsa Istanbul stock Exchange (BIST) for year 2010. Using OLS and two (2) stage least square regression analysis, auditing firm size, institutional ownership, independent directors, firm size, and corporate governance was positively associated with voluntary information disclosure. Ownership diffusion and Leverage were found to be negative and significant. Board size, listing age and Profitability were however, found to be positive but insignificant. Wang, Song and Yao (2013) studied a sample of eight hundred (800) firms listed on the Shanghai Stock Exchange in China from 2006 to 2015. Results from OLS regression showed that CSRD is positively associated with media exposure, firm size, institutional ownership, and ownership concentration.

Rouf (2011) used Ordinary Least Square (OLS) regression model to examine the relationship between firm characteristics and CSRD. From a sample of ninety three (93) companies listed on

the Dhaka Stock Exchange in year 2007, the study found that having independent directors on corporate boards has a significant positive relationship with CSR. Firm size was also found to have positive but insignificant relationship to CSR. Percentage return on equity, board leadership structure and board audit committee have positive and significant relationship with CSR. Said et al. (2009) studied the relationship between firm attributes and CSR in non-financial companies listed on the main board of the Bursa Malaysia in year 2006 using multiple regression analysis. The study discovered from a sample of 250 firms that government ownership, ownership concentration and audit committee have significant positive relationship with CSR, together with firm size and profitability is significant also. Foreign ownership, board independence, CEO duality, board size and managerial ownership were found to be positive but insignificant.

While studies such as Mohammed (2018) and Egbunike and Tarilaye (2017) have examined the relationship between company characteristics and CSR in Nigeria, few studies have focused on the relationship between ownership structure attributes and CSR. The few studies carried out have also produced mixed results. Ownership structure is an important concept that deals with the structure of shareholding in corporations. Hashim and Devi (2008) defined corporate ownership structure as the ratio of shares owned by large share investors to the total shares issued by the company. Thus, ownership structure describes the manner in which power and authority are distributed among shareholders (owners) in a company. Ownership structure in firms usually entail managerial ownership, institutional ownership, ownership concentration/block ownership (Ali & Isa, 2018), individual ownership, insider ownership, state/government ownership (Malik, Ahsan& Khan, 2017) and foreign ownership (Hassan, 2011).

Ownership structure is responsible for monitoring a corporations' disclosed information quality in its annual reports and also controls management behaviour to ensure that their actions are in line with the interests of stakeholders (Sadiq& Mohammed, 2017). Hence, corporate ownership structure can determine the extent of corporate monitoring, and this affects the quality of disclosures in corporate financial statements (Samaha&Dahawy, 2011). This study therefore empirically investigated the relationship between ownership structure and CSR in Nigeria, with focus on four (4) corporate ownership structure attributes (managerial ownership, institutional ownership, foreign ownership and ownership concentration) as variables. These corporate attributes were chosen because they are corporate attributes that explicitly show the power that shareholders can have in corporations especially when the shareholding structure is not balanced. This study also used a fixed effect model for panel regression analysis, which partials out the need for control variables in the panel regression analysis, as studies on ownership structure and CSR in Nigeria have used methods like OLS regression analysis (Sadiq & Mohammed, 2017) and probit regression analysis (Yusuf et al., 2018) which usually include the use of control variables like firm size and firm age (Yusuf et al., 2018). This study used both financial and non-financial companies listed on the NSE as at 31st December 2018. This is in contrast with

previous studies on ownership structure and CSR in Nigeria (Yusuf et al., 2018) which have focused on only financial companies listed on the NSE.

3.0 Methodology

The study used as population the one hundred and sixty-eight (168) companies listed on the NSE as at 31st December 2018 (NSE Fact book, 2018) due to the requirement for NSE listed companies to publish their financial statements, which makes data to be readily available to carry out the study. The financial statements of these companies were used to provide information on them from year 2009 to 2018. The sample size used for the study was derived with the Taro Yamane (1967) formula to ensure that the sample was scientifically chosen in order to reduce any bias in choosing the sample size. The one hundred and eighteen (118) financial and non-financial sample companies were selected through purposive sampling. This eliminates the companies that did not publish their annual financial reports in some of the years of the time frame (2009-2018) under study and also eliminates those companies that did not disclose all information on the selected independent variables (managerial ownership, institutional ownership, foreign ownership and ownership concentration) in some of the years. The financial statements of the sampled companies were used to provide data for the study from year 2009 to 2018. The study also adopts the longitudinal research design to enable it empirically investigate the relationship between ownership structure and CSR.

The study anchored on the agency theory as theoretical framework for empirically investigating the relationship between ownership structure and CSR. Agency theory was selected due to the fact that it best explained how management decisions are taken and policies made in corporations. It also best shows the relationship between owners and managers in a firm and the interplay of power between them. Thus, agency theory best describes how owners (shareholders) can influence management decisions and policies and how a firm's shareholding structure can also affect corporate decisions and actions, which the selected corporate characteristics (managerial ownership, institution ownership, foreign ownership and ownership concentration) portray in relation to the disclosing of CSR information.

This study therefore used an adapted version of the model by Yusuf *et al.* (2018) and the adapted model is stated in its functional form as;

$$CSR = f(MNOW, INOW, FOWN, OWCN)$$

The model as stated in its econometric form is;

$$CSR_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 MNOW_{it} + \beta_2 INOW_{it} + \beta_3 FOWN_{it} + \beta_4 OWCN_{it} + U'_{it}$$

Where; CSR= Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosures; MNOW= Managerial Ownership; INOW= Institutional Ownership; FOWN= Foreign Ownership; OWCN= Ownership Concentration; $\beta_0, \beta_1 \dots \beta_4$ = Constant term and regression coefficients; U'_{it} = Error term; i = Cross section (1...118); t = Time frame (1...10)

Operationalisation of Variables

VARIABLES	CODE	MEASUREMENTS
Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosures	CSR D	United Nations Global Compact standard for CSR D (Ortaset <i>et al.</i> , 2015). A company is scored one (1) if an item in the standard is disclosed and zero (0) if the item in the standard is not disclosed. The total score for each company is then divided by the maximum score of ten (10) which is the total number of items in the standard (Appendix I).
Managerial Ownership	MNOW	Percentage of equity shares held by directors of the company to the total number of equity shares issued (Yusuf <i>et al.</i> , 2018). The apriori expectation is $\beta_1 > 0$.
Institutional Ownership	INOW	Percentage of equity shares of the company held by institutional investors to the total number of equity shares issued (Yusuf <i>et al.</i> , 2018). The apriori expectation is $\beta_2 > 0$.
Foreign Ownership	FOWN	Percentage of equity shares owned by foreigners to the total number of equity shares issued (Laksmi&Kamila, 2018). The apriori expectation is $\beta_3 > 0$.
Ownership Concentration	OWCN	Percentage of equity shares owned by shareholders who own atleast 5% of total equity shares (Ba, 2017). The apriori expectation is $\beta_4 > 0$.

Source: Researcher's Compilation (2022)

Based on the empirical studies reviewed, the apriori expectations of the coefficients of the independent variables are given below as;

$$\beta_1, \beta_2 \dots \beta_4 > 0$$

This is in line with the agency theory and the empirical studies reviewed such as Ahmad *et al.* (2017) (institutional ownership) and Haladu and Salim (2017) (ownership concentration) have found a positive relationship between ownership structure attributes and CSR D.

This study used descriptive statistics, which include mean, median, maximum, minimum, standard deviation, skewness, kurtosis, Jarque-Bera, probability, sum and sum of square deviation, to analyse the data generated from the annual financial reports of the sampled listed companies. Correlation analysis is also used to analyse how the model variables are related. Panel regression analysis using fixed effect model, which partials out the need for control variables like firm size, is used for model estimation. The reason for this choice of regression technique for data analysis is that it enables the study of changes in complex behavioural models and minimises any bias that can arise from aggregating firms into groups.

4.0 Data Presentation, Analyses and Discussion of Results

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

Table 4.1 Results of the Descriptive Statistics

	CSR D	FOWN	IOWN	MOWN	OWCN
Mean	0.345886	0.131251	0.679862	0.073466	0.553704

Median	0.200000	0.000000	0.743100	0.009600	0.595900
Maximum	1.000000	0.973700	0.994900	0.877000	0.983000
Minimum	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000
Std. Dev.	0.239176	0.242869	0.237130	0.146586	0.221905
Skewness	1.559007	1.594241	-1.122704	3.111248	-0.466963
Kurtosis	4.726225	3.927539	3.656079	13.64520	2.526160
Jarque-Bera	623.9789	541.6888	268.8267	7468.953	53.87754
Probability	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000
Sum	407.8000	154.7455	801.5572	86.61638	652.8169
Sum Sq. Dev.	67.38755	69.48470	66.23951	25.31226	58.00671
Observations	1179	1179	1179	1179	1179

Source: Researchers Computation(2022)

CSR=Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosures; FOWN= Foreign Ownership; IOWN= Institutional Ownership; MOWN=Managerial Ownership; OWCN= Ownership Concentration

The result of the descriptive statistics as shown in table 4.1 reveals a mean CSR (corporate social responsibility disclosure) of 0.3459, which indicates that the sampled companies on the average disclose about 35% of CSR (corporate social responsibility) information in their annual financial reports. The results also reveal a mean foreign ownership (FOWN) of 13.13%, average institutional ownership (IOWN) of 68%, managerial ownership (MOWN) of about 7% and ownership concentration of 55%. The maximum value of the dependent variable CSR is 1 with a minimum value of 0. For the independent variables, foreign ownership has a maximum value of 0.97 and a minimum value of 0, institutional ownership has a maximum value of 0.99 and a minimum value of 0.00. The maximum value of the variable, managerial ownership is 0.87 and the minimum value is 0.00. Lastly, ownership concentration has a maximum value of 0.98 and a minimum value of 0.00.

4.2 Correlation Analysis

Table 4.2 Correlation Analysis

	CSR	FOWN	IOWN	MOWN	OWCN
CSR	1.000000	0.276008	-0.049726	-0.139080	-0.003309
FOWN	0.276008	1.000000	0.071868	-0.198844	0.211647
IOWN	-0.049726	0.071868	1.000000	-0.385891	0.320008
MOWN	-0.139080	-0.198844	-0.385891	1.000000	-0.031480
OWCN	-0.003309	0.211647	0.320008	-0.031480	1.000000

The result of the correlation coefficient revealed a mixed coefficient of both positive and negative values. The correlation coefficient between the dependent variable of CSRD and the independent variable of foreign ownership is positive with a value of 0.2760. The correlation coefficients between the dependent variable of CSRD and the independent variables of institutional ownership, managerial ownership and ownership concentration are all negative with values of -0.0497, -0.1390 and -0.0033 respectively. The correlation coefficients did not pose any problem of multicollinearity as the results of the correlation coefficients are relatively small. The highest value of correlation coefficient is between institutional ownership and ownership concentration with values of 0.3200.

4.3 Analysis of Regression Results

Table 4.3 Results of the Regression Analyses

VARIABLE	POOLED	RANDOM EFFECT	FIXED EFFECT
C	16.5454 (0.0000)	7.5878 (0.0000)	6.8603 (0.0000)
FOWN	9.0899 (0.0000)	-0.5002 (0.0000)	-4.4255 (0.0000)
IOWN	-3.4302 (0.0000)	1.5150 (0.1300)	2.3321 (0.0000)
MOWN	-4.1956 (0.0000)	-0.8330 (0.4050)	-3.3934 (0.0007)
OWCN	-0.9314 (0.3518)	2.2701 (0.0234)	4.2016 (0.0000)
R-squared	0.0964	0.0084	0.8251
Adjusted R-squared	0.0934	0.0050	0.8051
F-statistic	31.3430	2.4791	41.2101
Prob(F-statistic)	0.0000	0.0050	0.0000
Durbin-Watson Stat	0.3791	0.9494	1.0581
Redundant Fixed Effects Test			37.6351 (0.0000)
Hausman		30.4443 (0.0000)	
Observations	1179	1179	1179

Source: Researchers Computation (2022) (All variables are significant at the 5% level. The probability values are in parenthesis)

The result of the regression analysis shows the pooled, random effect and fixed effect regression analysis. The result of the redundant fixed effect with F-statistic value of 37.6351 and probability value of 0.0000 shows the pooled OLS is not adequate, hence, we proceed to test between fixed and random effects model. The result of the Hausman test with a probability value of 0.0000 and a Chi-sq value of 30.4444 shows preference for the fixed effect model. The result of the Hausman test rejects the null hypothesis of equality of coefficients between the random and fixed effect model. The fixed effect model has a coefficient of multiple correlation of 0.8251 with an adjusted R-square of 0.8051. The adjusted R-square value of 0.8051 shows that, about 82.51% of the systematic cross-sectional variation of the dependent variables of corporate social responsibility disclosure, is accounted for by the independent variables of foreign ownership, institutional ownership, managerial ownership and ownership concentration. The F-statistic value of 41.2101 obtained from the fixed effect model and the significant probability value of 0.0000 shows that a significant linear relationship exists between the dependent variable and the independent variables.

Furthermore, the result of the fixed effect regression analysis shows that our apriori expectation of $\beta_1 > 0$ could not be sustained with a t- value of -3.3934 and a probability value of 0.00. The result revealed a significant negative impact of managerial ownership on corporate social responsibility disclosure. This finding is inconsistent with that of Yusuf *et al.* (2018) and Sadiq and Mohammed (2017) who found a positive relationship. However, it supports the findings of Kurawa and Kabara (2014) and Chang and Zhang (2015) where a negative relationship was found. This significant negative impact implies that the more equity shares are owned by corporate managers, the less CSRDis made and when management own few shares, more CSRDis are made by firms listed on the NSE. This may be due to the fact that corporate managers in companies listed on the NSE may take advantage of their positions and promote their personal interests such as higher remuneration and executive bonus, above those of the shareholders, thus neglecting long term shareholder values of CSR and CSRDis. It may also be due to the fact that when managers own shares in companies, it may be more difficult for owners/shareholders to control and monitor them.

Agency theory predicts institutional ownership having a positive significant effect on CSRDis. In consonance with our apriori expectation of a positive effect, the fixed effect regression analysis reported a positive and statistically significant effect with a t-value of 2.3321 and probability value of 0.00. This finding is in line with those of Ahmad *et al.* (2017) and Chang and Zhang (2015) but debunks the findings of Yusuf *et al.* (2018) and Ghabayenet *al.* (2016). The result therefore suggests that the higher the equity shares owned by institutions such as pension funds, the higher the CSRDis carried out. This supports the idea that institutional shareholders seek to protect their usually large investments and thus use their high voting power which is derived from their large investments to influence the decisions of the management.

The result of the fixed effect regression analysis shows that our apriori expectation of $\beta_3 > 0$ could not be sustained with a t-value of -4.4255 and a probability value of 0.00. The result revealed a significant negative effect of foreign ownership on CSR. This suggests that as foreign ownership increases in NSE listed companies, CSR decreases. The result explains that foreign owners of equity shares in NSE listed firms are more interested in repatriating profits to their home countries than carrying out CSR and CSRs. This therefore negates the idea that foreign owners of shares protect their share investments by promoting social and environmental activities. Hence, the result is inconsistent with the findings of Hu *et al.* (2016) and Said *et al.* (2009) where a positive relationship was found but is consistent with the findings of Laksmi and Kamila (2018) where a negative relationship was found.

Agency theory predicts ownership concentration having a positive significant impact on CSR. In consonance with our apriori expectation of a positive effect, the fixed effect regression analysis reported a positive and statistically significant effect with a t-value of 4.2016 and probability value of 0.00. This reveals that as more equity share ownership is concentrated among a few shareholders, disclosure of CSR information increases. This may be due to the ability of these concentrated share owners to control and monitor management and also the need for them to protect their investments by ensuring the corporation has a positive public image. Also, the result reinforces the findings of Yusuf *et al.* (2018) and Chang and Zhang (2015) while it negates the findings of Mohamed and Faouzi (2014).

4.4 Conclusion

This study investigated the relationship between ownership structure and CSR in Nigeria with focus on four (4) ownership structure attributes, which includes managerial ownership, institutional ownership, foreign ownership and ownership concentration. It contributes to the existing body of knowledge on ownership structure and CSR using the UNGC (United Nations Global Compact), which very few studies have used as framework, to measure the impact of ownership structure attributes on the CSR of companies listed on the NSE. Also, the focus of this study was on the relationship between ownership structure and CSR among sampled NSE listed companies, CSR being a specific aspect of voluntary disclosures in Nigeria due to its voluntary nature.

Data analysis was carried out using descriptive statistics, correlation analysis and panel regression analysis using a fixed effect model. The result of the data analysis indicated that CSR in Nigeria is low with an average CSR of 35%, maximum CSR being 100% and minimum 0% in accordance with the principles of the UNGC. Average managerial ownership among firms listed on the NSE is 7%, average institutional ownership being 68%, with foreign ownership and ownership concentration having averages of 13.13% and 55% respectively.

Results for the correlation analysis revealed that managerial ownership, institutional ownership and ownership concentration are negatively related with CSRD while foreign ownership is positively related with CSRD. Institutional ownership and ownership concentration have the highest correlation while managerial ownership and institutional ownership have the lowest correlation. A significant linear relationship is found to exist between the independent variables (managerial ownership, institutional ownership, foreign ownership and ownership concentration) and the dependent variable (CSRD).

The regression results suggest that among firm listed on the NSE, managerial ownership and foreign ownership have a significant negative effect on CSRD in Nigeria which negates the apriori expectation for managerial and foreign ownership. This means that as managerial and foreign ownership of shares increase, CSRD decreases. Institutional ownership and ownership concentration also have a significant positive effect on CSRD which emphasizes the apriori expectation for institutional ownership and ownership concentration. This means that when Institutions own large amount of shares and share ownership is concentrated in the hands of few investors, CSRD increases.

In view of the research findings of this study and its contribution to knowledge, the study recommends that the voluntary nature of CSRD in Nigeria should be enhanced through the enactment of compulsory regulations on CSRD as this will aid increase in the low level of CSRD. Also the capital market through the Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC) should regulate the issue of share in companies through ensuring that management should not be allowed to own large amounts of equity shares in order to increase CSRD in Nigeria. Institutional shareholders should also be allowed to own large amounts of equity shares in Nigeria as this leads to increased levels of CSRD. Foreign ownership of equity shares should be reduced as this will increase CSRD levels in Nigeria. Ownership concentration should also be encouraged in Nigeria especially when such concentration is in the hands of institutional shareholders in order to increase CSRD levels. Institutional shareholders should be allowed and encouraged to have representatives on the board of directors which represents corporate management, as this will help to strengthen the relationship between institutional shareholders and their company's management as institutional shareholders promote increased levels of CSRD in NSE (Nigeria Stock Exchange) listed companies.

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